

vae tiller⁻¹ with only 7% live larvae hill⁻¹. These results suggest that the larvae did not bore into or remain inside the sheaths of IR40 because it is a poor host.

Early larval mortality is a resistance mechanism that is complementary to the ability of rice plants to compensate for YSB

injury at the vegetative stage (Rubia et al 1990, 1996). We found that the greater the number of tillers uninfected by YSB larvae, the faster the rice plants compensate for injury because there are enough assimilates to produce new tillers (unpubl. data).

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Effects of the ladybird beetle *Micraspis discolor* on yield components and grain yield of rice

N.Afsana and Z. Islam, Entomology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh
E-mail: islamz@bangla.net

Micraspis (= *Verania*) *discolor* Fab. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) preys on several rice pests (Samal and Misra 1985, Shepard and Rapusas 1989) and also feeds on rice pollen (Pathak and Khan 1994). *M. discolor* pollen feeding on rice panicles increases at flowering in all three rice seasons—boro (winter rice), aus (summer rice), and T. aman (monsoon rice)—in Bangladesh (Rahman et al 1991). A study was undertaken to determine the effects of pollen feeding by adult *M. discolor* at different population densities on yield components and grain yield of rice.

To test the effects of 0, 2, 5, 10, and 20 adult *M. discolor* rice hill⁻¹ on yield components and grain yield, we conducted an experiment on the experimental farm of BRRI in Gazipur, Bangladesh, in the 1990 boro season. The experiment was using a completely randomized block design with 10 replications. A field where BRRI Dhan 29 was planted at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm was divided into fifty 2 × 2-m plots and a single hill was selected

randomly in each plot. Adult *M. discolor* were confined on selected rice hills by white fine-mesh nylon net cages measuring 20 × 20 × 120 cm (length × breadth × height). Another set of 10 rice hills was marked but not covered by nylon mesh cages and kept free from *M. discolor* by hand-picking to determine whether shading at flowering and early grain filling affects grain filling and grain yield. Mesh cages and *M. discolor* beetles were removed 20 d after confinement, when panicles of all tillers either reached or passed the milky stage. We recorded the

number of panicles hill⁻¹, the number of filled and unfilled grains panicle⁻¹, and grain weight (adjusted to 14% moisture content).

On average, there were 11.8–13.3 panicles hill⁻¹ and panicle densities between treatments were similar (see table). An *M. discolor* density of 2–20 hill⁻¹ did not affect filled grain number panicle⁻¹, average panicle weight, individual grain weight, grain sterility, and grain yield. Rice hills that were not covered by the mesh cage had a significantly lower sterility ($P < 0.01$) and more filled

Effects of pollen feeding by *M. discolor* on yield components and grain yields of rice (var. BRRI Dhan 29), BRRI farm, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1999.^a

<i>M. discolor</i> density (no. hill ⁻¹)	Panicles (no. hill ⁻¹)	Filled grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	Panicle weight (g)	Individual grain wt. (mg)	Sterility (%)	Yield (g hill ⁻¹)
0	12.3 a	72.8 b	1.5 b	20.48 a	46.6a	18.3 a
2	11.8 a	82.6 ab	1.7 ab	20.33 a	47.2 a	19.2 a
5	13.1 a	75.9 b	1.6 ab	20.85 a	51.1 a	19.8 a
10	13.3 a	75.6 b	1.6 ab	21.69 a	48.6 a	20.9 a
20	11.8 a	78.2 ab	1.7 ab	20.55 a	46.2 a	19.0 a
0 (not enclosed)	12.4 a	91.2 a	1.8 a	20.16 a	34.5 b	22.7 a
<i>P</i> <	ns	0.05	0.05	ns	0.01	ns
CV%	25.1	19.9	20.9	14.1	17.8	26.0

^aData are av of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. CV = coefficient of variation. ns = not significant.

grains panicle⁻¹ ($P < 0.05$) than plants covered by the mesh cage without *M. discolor* beetles. Grain yields, however, were similar, indicating that shading affects yield components. Our results showed that rice pollen feeding by *M. discolor* even at high population densities did not increase grain sterility or affect filled grain number, grain filling, and grain yield. Therefore, it can be con-

cluded that, although *M. discolor* has a phytophagous habit, it is not a pest of rice.

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Effects of rice hispa damage on grain yield

S.S. Haque and Z. Islam, Entomology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRR), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh
 E-mail: islamz@bangla.net

Rice hispa [*Dicladispa armigera* (Olivier) (Chrysomelidae: Coleoptera)] is a major rice pest in Bangladesh. Adults feed on the green tissue of the leaf blade externally and grubs are leaf miners. Rice hispa (RH) prefers young rice plants, but, in their absence, it also attacks maturing plants. Some reports estimate time- and space-specific damage ranging from 14% to 62% yield losses from RH (Alam 1977, Karim 1987, Islam 1989, Chatterjee and Bera 1990, Nath and Dutta 1997). However, the relationship between damage level and grain loss is not clear. Therefore, we carried out several experiments at BRR under irrigated conditions in the 1999 aus (summer rice) and transplant aman (monsoon rice) seasons.

To simulate leaf damage in BR3 in the aus season and BRR Dhan 32 in the T. aman season at different plant growth stages, adult RH beetles were confined at different densities—0, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 beetles tiller⁻¹. In total, seven experiments were conducted in a randomized complete

block design with four replications. Rice plants were protected from other insect pests by applying granular insecticide (diazinon 5G) at recommended doses well before or after the treatment. In the aus season, experiments were conducted at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DAT) and at 20, 30, 50, and 70 DAT in the T. aman season. Unit plot size was 2 m × 2 m. Four rice hills (except border hills) were selected and marked in each plot. Tiller and leaf numbers were counted. Leaf damage was achieved by confining RH beetles on selected hills by a white nylon mesh cage. After 12–15 d of confinement, when the desired

level of leaf damage was achieved, beetles and cages were removed. Leaf damage was estimated visually (0–100%). Grain yields were estimated by harvesting four marked hills plot⁻¹. Yields were adjusted to 14% moisture content.

In the aus season, different densities of RH caused about 9–89% leaf damage at 20 DAT, 5–69% at 40 DAT, and 3–36% at 60 DAT, suggesting increased resistance against RH feeding with plant age. Rice plants recovered from the damage by producing new leaves. The effect of RH density on grain yield was not significant (see table).

Effect of different densities of rice hispa beetles on grain yield of rice (BR3) in the summer rice season, BRR farm, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1999.*

Hispa density (no. tiller ⁻¹)	Grain yield (g 4 hills ⁻¹)			
	20 DAT	40 DAT	60 DAT	Mean
0	99.5	74.5	95.5	89.8
0.2	83.6	94.8	98.5	92.3
0.5	102.9	80.6	93.5	92.3
1	90.2	95.8	90.7	92.2
2	85.3	83.5	100.6	89.8
4	80.4	95.9	107.5	94.6
Mean	90.3	87.5	97.7	91.8
P	ns	ns	ns	ns

*DAT = days after transplanting. Rice hispa was allowed to incur damage for 12–15 d.